

Acidoid Behaviour of Charcoal as a Function of its Oxygen Complexes. Part V. Interaction of Charcoal and Amines

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Adsorption of *n*-butyl, dimethyl, diethyl, and triethyl amines in aqueous solutions by sugar charcoal before and after outgassing at different temperatures is a neutralising reaction involving the acidic sites provided by the CO₂-complex and as such it is largely dependent on the nature of the surface. The rest of the chemisorbed oxygen does not appear to have any effect.

It has been shown in the earlier publications¹ that charcoal by virtue of the presence of CO₂-complex along its surface undergoes surface ionisation, when suspended in water, as

where the circle represents the charcoal surface. The hydrogen ions being directed towards the liquid phase can neutralise stoichiometric amounts of different alkalies, equivalent to the amount of the CO₂-complex. The present communication describes the interaction of charcoal, coated with varying amounts of oxygen and hydrogen complexes, and different kinds of amines. It may be mentioned that Phelps and Peters² from a study of the adsorption of simple aliphatic amines and Kipling³ from a study of the adsorption of *n*-butylamine on activated charcoal arrived at the conclusion that the process, in every case, took place through undissociated molecules and was essentially physical in nature and independent of the chemical or electrochemical nature of the surface. Bodfors and Inge Ehrlen⁴ also from the adsorption study of mono-, di- and tri-methyl and -ethyl amines on active charcoal did not consider the nature of the surface to be of much consequence. Anderson and Emmett⁵, on the other hand, showed that the adsorption of methylamine by a carbon black was influenced by the nature of the surface and that the adsorption in excess of a monolayer in the case of oxygen-containing blacks could be attributed to the polarity of the molecules and their ability to form hydrogen bonds with the constituents of the oxygen complex. The present work shows the importance of a part of the combined oxygen and the structure of the amino molecules in influencing the magnitude of the interaction of charcoal and amines of different kinds.

1. Puri *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1957, 34, 357; 1958, 35, 189; 1959, 36, 835; 1960, 37, 207.
2. *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1929, 124A, 554.
3. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 1493.
4. *Kgl. Fysiograf. Salls Kap. Lond. Forh.*, 1945, 15, 3.
5. *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1952, 56, 756.
6. Puri *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 4880.
7. Puri *et al.*, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1958, 62, 756.
8. Puri *et al.*, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1958, 50, 1071.

EXPERIMENTAL

Sugar charcoal, prepared in the same manner as described earlier⁶, was used as such (when it is referred to as 'original' charcoal in the text) as well as after outgassing at 300°, 400°, 500°, 600°, 750°, 900°, 1000°, and 1200°. The method of evacuation has been described before⁶. The samples were allowed to cool in vacuum and were then transferred to well-stoppered bottles. The amounts of oxygen and hydrogen retained and their disposition as CO₂, CO, H₂O, and free hydrogen were determined in the manner described earlier⁶⁻⁷. The results are recorded in Table I. It is seen that the oxygen that comes off as carbon dioxide or as water decreases more rapidly than the oxygen that comes off as carbon monoxide. Thus the charcoal outgassed at 750° contains little or nothing of oxygen capable of evolving water and carbon dioxide but retains appreciable amounts of oxygen capable of evolving carbon monoxide. The elementary hydrogen decreases to an appreciable extent only when the charcoal is outgassed at 900° or above.

TABLE I

Amounts of gases evolved on evacuating diff. samples of sugar charcoal at 1200°.

Samples.	Gases evolved (in mg./g.) on evacuation.				Total oxygen (mg./g.).
	H ₂ O.	CO ₂ .	CO.	H ₂ .	
Original	80.6	151.1	129.3	15.2	255.4
Evacuated at 300°	75.7	78.9	129.0	15.2	197.4
400°	57.5	58.3	119.3	15.1	161.7
500°	48.9	27.5	113.0	15.1	126.2
600°	44.0	10.5	99.2	14.8	103.4
750°	15.1	Nil	97.0	12.0	68.8
900°	Nil	„	20.0	2.4	11.4
1000°	„	„	10.0	1.1	5.7
1200°	„	„	Nil	Nil	0.0

Adsorption of Bases.—Adsorption of *n*-butylamine, dimethylamine, diethylamine, and triethylamine, all of B. D. H. chemically pure quality, was studied. Charcoal (1 g.) was shaken with an aqueous solution (100 ml) of the amine of desired concentration in a stoppered bottle for a definite period after which an aliquot of the clear supernatant liquid was titrated against a standard solution of HCl, using bromocresol green as the indicator. A blank was also run simultaneously.

In some of the experiments, the treated charcoal was washed repeatedly over filter paper with CO₂-free distilled water till the filtrate did not change the colour (blue) of bromothymol blue indicator to yellow. The pH values of the aqueous suspensions (1:5) of the washed charcoals varied between 7.1 and 7.4.

The capacity of each charcoal to neutralise barium hydroxide was also determined as in the previous investigations^{6,7,8} by shaking 1-g. portion with 100 ml of 0.2*N* solution for about 48 hr. and titrating an aliquot of the clear supernatant liquid against a standard acid solution in the usual way.

TABLE II

Samples.	n -BuNH ₂ neutralised (m.e./100g.).	Ba(OH) ₂ neutralised (m.e./100 g.).	CO ₂ evolved (m.e./100 g.).
Original	703	682	687
Evacuated at 300°	379	361	359
400°	209	260	265
500° ^a	140	128	125
600°	52	45	48
750°	Nil	Nil	Nil
900°	"	"	"
1000°	"	"	"
1200°	"	"	"

DISCUSSION

The effect of time of shaking and the effect of concentration of the solution employed on the magnitude of the reaction of the original charcoal with the various amines are shown graphically in Fig. 1 and 2. It is seen that ultimately a definite limiting value can be obtained by using about 0.7 *N* solution in the case of *n*-butylamine and about 0.4 *N* solution in other amines and by shaking the suspensions for about 50 hours in every case.

FIG. 1. Effect of concentrations of amine solution on the amount neutralised by charcoal.

(a) *n*-Butylamine. (b) Diethylamine. (c) Diethylamine. (d) Triethylamine.

The amounts of *n*-butylamine, neutralised under these conditions by the various samples of charcoal, are recorded in Table II. The corresponding barium hydroxide values and the amounts of CO₂ evolved on evacuation, expressed in similar units, are also included in the same table. It is seen that the amount of *n*-butylamine taken up by each sample is fairly close to that of barium hydroxide neutralised by it and that both values are of about

the same order as the amount of CO_2 evolved. This shows that the adsorption of *n*-butylamine from aqueous solution by charcoal under appropriate conditions is primarily a neutralising reaction as that of any other base^{10,11} on account of the presence of the acidic CO_2 -complex. This view receives further support from the fact that when the CO_2 -complex is eliminated completely on outgassing the charcoal at 750° or at higher temperatures (Table I), the material loses its capacity to take up the amine as well as barium hydroxide. Thus the adsorption of *n*-butylamine involves the same mechanism as the adsorption of any other base and therefore, on analogy, may be represented as

In other words, the interaction merely involves the replacement of the surface hydrogen ions by the amine cations.

FIG. 2. Effect of time of shaking on the amount of amine neutralised by charcoal. (a) *n*-Butylamine. (b) Dimethylamine. (c) Diethylamine. (d) Triethylamine.

It may also be noted that the charcoal, outgassed at 750° , retains an appreciable amount of oxygen (about 5.5%) capable of evolving carbon monoxide, but it can neither adsorb *n*-butylamine nor barium hydroxide. Therefore the view of some of the workers that the whole of the chemisorbed oxygen is involved in the adsorption of amines³ or alkalis^{10,11} is not substantiated.

The values for dimethyl, diethyl, and triethyl amines have been found to be appreciably lower than those for *n*-butylamine in each sample, although the dissociation constants of all the four amines are known to be fairly close to one another. The results obtained in the case of the original sugar charcoal are recorded in Table III. It is seen that the neutralisation value decreases with increase in the number of the hydrocarbon chains in the amine and that for a given type of amine, the value decreases with increase in the length of the hydrocarbon chain (cf. values for dimethyl and diethyl amines). There can be little doubt that adsorption in each case takes place at the same acid sites provided by the CO_2 -complex since the values (not included in the table) decrease on outgassing the charcoal in proportion to the amount of the CO_2 -complex eliminated and disappeared with complete elimination of the complex at 750° .

10. Wilson and Bolam, *J. Colloid Sci.*, 1950, 5, 550.

11. Weller and Young, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 70, 4155.

TABLE III

Amines.	Amount neutralised (m.e./100g.)		Ratio of diameter of <i>n</i> -butylamine given amines	Amt. retained after washing (m.e./100 g.).
	Expt.	Calc.		
<i>n</i> -Butylamine	703	..	1.00	280
Dimethylamine	548	500	0.78	253
Diethylamine	400	436	0.57	223
Triethylamine	301	320	0.43	206

The discrepancy in the magnitude of the adsorption of the four amines examined appears to arise from the orientation factors. It seems reasonable to surmise that the basic amino group, in each case is oriented towards the acid sites provided by the CO₂-complex. In the case of *n*-butylamine, the single hydrocarbon chain projecting vertically and sharply out of the middle of the pyrimidal nitrogen atom is not expected to cover any noticeable portion of the charcoal surface, but in the case of secondary and tertiary amines, the presence of more than one hydrocarbon chain will introduce steric effects, as can be shown by models, and therefore some of the active sites provided by the CO₂-complex may not be available for similar orientation of their molecules. The relative proportions of the sites rendered inaccessible in this manner, will evidently be more in tertiary than in secondary amines; amongst the secondary amines, the effect will be more in diethylamine than in dimethylamine. Assuming that there is no steric effect in *n*-butylamine and that in the other amines this effect varies as the diameter of the molecule representing distance between extreme hydrogen atoms of the alkyl radicals attached to the nitrogen atom, it follows that the ratio of adsorbability of *n*-butylamine to that of any other amine varies inversely as the ratio of their molecular diameters. The ratios of the molecular diameters of dimethyl, diethyl, and triethyl amines to that of *n*-butylamine, as obtained from the models, are shown in Table III. The adsorbabilities of the various amines calculated from these considerations will be considered to be fairly close, keeping in view the approximations involved. This agreement indicates that the adsorption of all types of amines by charcoal takes place at the same sites.

Amounts of the various amines, retained by the original charcoal after exhaustive washings with water, when the treated material in each case is brought down to the same pH range of 7.1-7.4, are seen (column 5) to be much closer to one another than the amounts originally neutralised (column 2). This agreement further supports the view that adsorption of amines of all types by charcoal is a neutralisation reaction, which, as shown in the preceding paragraphs, is largely influenced by presence of the CO₂-complex.